

LINGUISTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF PHRASEOLOGISMS INVOLVING CLOTHES NAMES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqola leksikologiyaning bir bo‘limi frazeologiya sohasiga bag‘ishlangan bo‘lib, unda asosan ingliz va o‘zbek tillarida kiyim –kechak nomlari ishtirokidagi frazeologizmlarning lingvomadaniy jihatdan qiyosiy tahlil qilinib, ma‘lum bir millatning mentaliteti, madaniyati, urf-odatlar va an‘analarini o‘zida aks ettirgan frazeologik birliklar haqida qimmatli ma‘lumotlar beriladi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: fraza, kiyim-kechak nomlari, frazeologizm, komparativ iboralar, lingvomadaniyat.

Аннотация. *Данная статья является частью лексикологии, посвященной области фразеологии, в которой фразеология с названиями одежды на английском и узбекском языках в основном анализируется с лингвокультурологической точки зрения, а также менталитет, культура, обычаи и традиции определенного анализируются нации, даются ценные сведения о фразеологизмах, отражающих их мать.*

Ключевые слова: словосочетание, названия одежды, фразеологизм, компаративные выражения, лингвокультура.

Abstract. *This article is devoted to the field of phraseology, a section of lexicology, which mainly includes names of clothes in English and Uzbek languages. Phraseologisms are comparatively analyzed from a linguistic and cultural point of view, and valuable information is given about phraseological units that reflect the mentality, culture, customs and traditions of a certain nation.*

Key words: phrase, names of clothing, phraseologism, comparative expressions, linguistic culture.

INTRODUCTION

Linguistics is a general science that arose between the sciences of cultural studies and linguistics, and studies such phenomena as the interaction and connection of language and culture, the formation of this connection and its reflection outside language as a whole system is

engaged in learning. On the one hand, linguocultural science studies the place of humanity in the cultural language factor, and on the other hand, the place of man in the language factor. Each language is closely related to the history of its speakers and contains some special aspects of their traditional daily life, geography, and culture that have not been written about shows.

Every language undoubtedly affects the culture of its speakers. Our students studying a foreign language face difficulties in understanding the essence of the original meanings hidden in the expressions of other nations until they learn the culture and ways of thinking of that nation. A lot has been written about phraseological units, they are grammatical, semantically and syntactically analyzed, but linguistically and culturally insufficiently researched.

The relationship between language and culture was expressed for the first time by the German scientist V. von Humboldt in his works as follows: A person's language conveys information about the subject in such a way that it lives. Any language expresses the people to which a person belongs, his way of life.

M.M.Pokrovsky, G.V.Stepanov, A.A.Potebnya, D.S.Likhachev and Y.M.Lotman, F.I.Busayev, as a result of their research, scientifically based linguistic and cultural studies as a science.

In Uzbek linguistics, the first studies devoted to linguistic and cultural studies were conducted by Sh. Safarov, D. Khudoyberganov, N. Mahmudov and Sh.Usmanova. In recent years, great importance has been attached to the study of Uzbek phraseology in comparison with other languages from a linguocultural, cognitive scientific point of view. Among them, B.Safaraliyev, G.Bakiyeva, N.Nasrullayeva semantically define expressions as religious, legendary, historical, related to literature, geographical and national researched into conceptual areas. Professor A. Mamatov points out that expressions are formed in different ways from a historical etymological point of view. In the scientist's opinion, he emphasizes that phraseological units are formed on the basis of Uzbek reality, and secondly, phraseologisms that have entered from related and non-related languages through appropriation and imitation.

Shavkat Rahmatullayev in the book “Annotated Phraseological Dictionary of the Uzbek Language” mentions that the main part of phrases in Uzbek linguistics is made up of verb phraseological units, as well as phrases with a noun component, adjective and adverbial component.

Main Part. The names of clothes and shoes are often found in English idioms. Such expressions are hundreds of years old, their original connection with clothing has already been erased, so they are difficult to understand and remember. We have selected idioms for clothes, pants, shirt, shoes and other items of clothing. To make them easier to remember, we talk about their origin, literal meaning, interesting facts and ways of using them in speech.

Literally means “**eat your hat**”. This is how they express confidence in the success of a business: “**I’ll eat my hat if it’s not so**”. The first time the expression occurs in the work of Thomas Bridges. And Charles Dickens, in The Posthumous Papers of the Pickwick Club, added to the idiom:

I’d eat my hat and swallow the buckle whole. “I’ll eat my hat and swallow the clasp. **Below the belt** - unfair, dishonest.

Literally – “**below the belt.**” The origin of the phrase is not difficult to guess. This idiom is similar to the Russian expression “low blow”, so it’s easy to remember. In this case, the English expression does not need to use the word “strike”, for example:

Your attitude to my wedding is below the belt. “Your treatment of my wedding is unfair. Old hat - an outdated, unfashionable thing.

“**Old hat**” - this is what they say not only about clothes, but also about other things: appliances, furniture, jewelry. This can also be said about people - for example, the elderly or those with outdated views.

Old hat is synonymous with out of fashion. A phrase with this meaning appeared in English at the beginning of the 20th century. Interestingly, in the old version of English, the phrase old hat had a much more vulgar meaning: this was the name of the female organs, which are literally “**below the belt**”.

Your TV is an old hat, why don't you buy a flat screen TV? Your TV is outdated, why don't you buy a flat screen TV?

Wear the trousers, wear the pants - to be in charge.

So they say about the headship in the family, in the house, especially if this role is performed by a woman. The expression has already lost its original meaning of “**wearing trousers**”, but is still in use in the colloquial language. Note that Americans say wear the trousers, and English say wear the pants.

It is Mary who actually wears trousers in their relationship. - In fact, Mary is the main one in their relationship.

Cut from the same cloth - the same, similar. In English, there are two idioms with a similar meaning, but they are related to food: “the apple does not fall far from the tree” or “made from the same dough. And for native English speakers, similar people or things evoke a different association - as if cut from the same fabric. In the old days, English families bought one piece of fabric for everyone, from which clothes were sewn for all family members. It turned out to be similar, and relatives could be identified by the pattern or texture of the fabric.

Alan and his friend are cut from the same cloth. Alan and his friend are very similar. A wolf in sheep's clothing - pretend to be kind.

Literally means “**a wolf in sheep's clothing**”, the same expression is in Russian. According to the Bible, this is what Jesus said in his sermon: “Beware of false prophets, which come to you in sheep's clothing, but inwardly they are ravening wolves.” This expression is found in modern English and refers to conniving people who pretend to be good-natured.

Emily looks charming, but she is a wolf in sheep's clothing. Emily looks charming, but she's faking it.

Birthday suit - naked, naked.

Literally, the expression means “**birthday suit**”. You can guess the meaning of the idiom if you think about the first birthday and remember the Russian proverb “**in what the mother gave birth.**”

In a few minutes we were all in our birthday suits and in the water. “After a few minutes, we completely undressed and climbed into the water. (Charles D. Kipp, Linda Sykes, “Because We Are Canadians”)

With hat in hand - humbly, servilely, obsequiously.

The expression “**With a hat in hand**” refers to the times when the British wore hats. The hat was removed from the head and held in the hands as a sign of respect. Now this gesture is no longer used, but the

phrase has been preserved in the language. So often they say about asking people. In the sentence, the phrase **with hat in hand** serves as an introductory construction.

With hat in hand, he asked for salary raise.- He humbly asked for a raise.

Keep your shirt on / keep your pants on - keep calm. When unflappable English people ask you not to lose your temper, they literally say “do not take off your shirt or trousers”. This idiom is often used to calm nervous, agitated people.

The origin of the expression is not entirely clear. Perhaps this was said about people who got so angry that they got into a fight, taking off their shirt as they went. Clothing constrains movement, so before fights and fights it was removed. And angry people, ready to rush into battle, were so calmed, urging them not to take off their shirts.

Mark didn't mean anything bad, keep your shirt on. Mark didn't mean anything bad, calm down.

CONCLUSION

Studying phrases in both languages, revealing their semantic-grammatical and functional stylistic features determines the relevance of this work. However, expressions with adjective components are an unexplored field within these languages. It is known that expressions are inextricably linked with the spirituality, culture, customs, lifestyle and history of the people who own the language. Based on this point of view in the article about 10 expressions containing clothes were studied, and the manifestation of the culture of the two nations in the language, their mutual influence and connection were considered. The opinions of linguists were studied and general conclusions were given to them.

In the course of the research, phraseological units with a clothing component in English and Uzbek languages were separated and analyzed morphologically, semantically and linguistically. The analysis shows that despite the fact that English and Uzbek nationalities are different from each other, the meaning of expressions composed of adjectives is very close to each other. Most of them are human qualities or defects in both languages serves to describe. The linguistic and cultural content of

selected idiomatic expressions from the English and Uzbek languages was explained.

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